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Lead Beneficiary (acronym)	SAI
Lead Scientist responsible for the report (Name, Institution)	Joan Nymand Larsen, Stefansson Arctic Institute, Akureyri, Iceland
Editors (Name, Institution)	Joan Nymand Larsen, Stefansson Arctic Institute, Akureyri, Iceland Susanna Gartler, University of Vienna, Austria Alexandra Meyer, University of Vienna, Austria Jon Haukur Ingimundarson, Stefansson Arctic Institute, Akureyri, Iceland Olga Povoroznyuk, University of Vienna, Austria Peter Schweitzer, University of Vienna, Austria

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1. Introduction

This report presents first an overview of a theoretical risk framework, including a Compass Model and Methodological Flow Chart, developed to help facilitate the gathering of coastal risks in a systematic way, to make assessments and apply different tools and analysis to contribute to more effective risk management at the local level in Arctic coastal communities. The development of this framework is motivated by the fact that thawing permafrost creates risks to the environment, economy, and culture of affected Arctic coastal communities, and more effective identification of these risks and the inclusion of the societal context and co-production with local stakeholders can provide the basis for effective risk management, reduced risks, and a more sustainable future (Larsen et al. 2021). This framework guides the interaction between different scientific workpackages and local communities, and thereby helps facilitate collaboration and co-production of knowledge in large-scale applied research projects such as Nunataryuk.

The risk framework and modelling was developed during the Nunataryuk project period and has provided the framework for identifying key risks from permafrost thaw in case study regions along the Arctic Coast; Ilulissat, West Greenland; Longyearbyen, Svalbard; Beaufort Sea Region, Yukon Coast and Mackenzie River Delta; and Northern Sakha (Yakutiya), Russia. We first demonstrate the use of the risk framework by presenting a generalized risk analysis that highlights five key hazards of permafrost thaw, as well as key physical processes/drivers that lead to physical, chemical and biological impacts that create five key hazards. Secondly, we present a risk diagram (which will appear in the Atlas of Permafrost in 2023), which shows the impacts of permafrost thaw along the Arctic coast. Next, we present local specific risk data from research conducted within the four case study areas, including results from a survey. A central element within the risk framework presented here is the notion of the dual dimensions of risk – the recognition of risk as both physical and socially constructed – and the importance of risk perceptions of permafrost affected Arctic communities, which facilitate the coproduction of knowledge.

Overall, our case studies show that permafrost thaw in local communities along the Arctic coast has negative impacts for all of the central quality of life domains, with risks to infrastructure and built environment, economy and planning being particularly challenging and necessitating critical trade-offs for many local stakeholders, including from private and public sectors.

2. Risk Analysis – Theoretical Risk Framework within Nunataryuk

The notion of “risk” occupies a central place in the conceptual framework of Nunataryuk. This was already highlighted in the original project proposal and further developed in a series of workshops, often held in conjunction with Nunataryuk General assemblies (e.g., in Venice in 2018 and in Nice in 2019). A final conceptual step was conducted during an in-person workshop in Copenhagen in February 2022, which resulted in the elaboration of the Risk Analysis

Framework consisting of a so-called *Compass Model* and a *Methodological Flow Chart* (see also Larsen et al. 2021).

As the Nunataryuk project is focused on permafrost thaw, we are using “risk” through the lens of thawing permafrost and its environmental, socio-economic, and cultural impacts on Arctic coastal communities. We believe that understanding these risks will enable communities to better address them and thereby to reach a higher level of sustainability.

While there is agreement that a risk is an actual or potential threat to something, which a particular group of people values, there are differences of opinion as to who is entitled to define such threats. Typically, this task is left to “experts”, most often external scientists and technical personnel. What distinguishes our project is that we do not limit ourselves to risks identified by experts but proactively include risk perceptions from within the community in question, that is the way and degree risks are recognized locally, no matter whether these perceptions coincide with expert risk assessments or not. The recognition of the dual dimensions of risk as both physical (and scientifically measurable) and socially constructed has important consequences for both risk appraisal, as well as for the knowledge production process more generally, as it sees local and indigenous knowledge as a necessary element of the process.

Our *Conceptual Risk Model*, the so-called *Compass Model*, is an inductive framework based on community and scientific input. It proposes guidance to the identification of risk and consequent development of adaptation and mitigation strategies in large, multidisciplinary projects working in multiple field sites. Its goal is to assist the interaction between different components of scientific work and the needs of local communities. It works in parallel to the processual model (see below), by providing an attractive tool which can be used by different stakeholders for identifying key risks and the processes leading to them.

The Compass Model shown here can be adapted to make it more appropriate for the respective social worlds, within both the different work packages of the project, as well as in the different sites where Nunataryuk operates. For example, the five categories of the Inuvialuit Regional Corporation report on climate change (IRC 2016) used in the compass model could be replaced by a different categorizing system, for example, the human security approach.

The first step was to compile risks for each of the field sites, which was achieved through incorporating several sources of input from scientists, local residents, and other stakeholders. Experts from different fields of

science provided scientific assessments of risks in the various domains of terrestrial, coastal and subsea permafrost, coastal waters, infrastructure, health and pollution, and natural resources and economy. In a second step, a series of participatory risk workshops in each of the field sites provided open spaces for the communication and discussion of both the scientifically assessed and locally perceived risks. Scientific experts and local knowledge holders exchanged information and concerns, evaluate each of the risks, and reached a consensus regarding key risks in every community. These identified key risks were fed back into the scientific work packages, guiding the subsequent work in the different field sites. In a fourth step, a final workshop or similar event in all participating communities will inform the public about the outcomes of the studies.

This process ensures that local concerns are taken into account and guides the study design of the project, making sure that the outcomes of the risk assessment are relevant to local partners and residents of places, where primary data gathering occurs. Instead of only identifying key risks, which local communities are more often than not already acutely aware of, the outcomes of the diverse studies should feed directly into the development of adaptation and mitigation strategies. Another advantage of the compass model is that it connects more easily (relative to other models) with the everyday lives of laypeople. A compass, a widely known symbolic representation of orientation and travel, also points to the cyclical nature of the seasonal round and of life itself.

Our *Processual Model*, a *Methodological Flow Chart* (see below)—demonstrates how to implement what has been outlined in the conceptual model. It supports its users in the process of carrying out systematic data gathering. In our case, we worked in field sites in four countries – Canada, Denmark (Greenland), Norway (Svalbard), and Russia) – collecting qualitative and quantitative data from a variety of natural and social science disciplines. Data inserted into the model can consist of observed changes, computational models, stakeholder concerns, etc. After gathering all risks, the scientists together with community representatives carry out a risk ranking. The different risks collected as part of the data collection are ranked based on a variety of factors, such as word counts, or perceived level of exposure and threat/risk. The most important final step is to have interactive communication about the results between the scientists and impacted communities experiencing risk, which – in most field sites – is yet to come. Risk evaluation can help communities decide how to spend the limited funds available in a way that optimizes their perception of quality of life. We suggest that the end-goal of the processual flow chart model is to gather risk systematically, make assessments and apply different tools and analyses that can empower Arctic coastal communities in facing permafrost thaw risks.

Overall, our aim with the development of a risk framework was to arrive at a model that can facilitate the gathering of risks in the Arctic coastal zone, in order to better manage and respond to permafrost thaw risks, and to empower local communities in the process. Our

proposed framework combines a conceptual and a processual model and seems particularly appropriate for large multidisciplinary projects, such as Nunataryuk. As mentioned above, what distinguishes our conceptual framework is the focus on the dual dimensions of risk and the importance of risk perceptions of the affected communities. Risk is thus seen as both a physical reality and a social construction. At the same time, our model framework recognizes that not one risk definition will fit all cases studied. Instead, our model provides room for different risk definitions.

Our next step involved bringing this framework to life in the context of several community risk workshops. The goal was to identify key socio-economic and cultural risks and to analyse the potential for reducing the level of risks from thawing permafrost. Eventually, this will lead to the development of a framework for risk management adjusted to Arctic coastal contexts. This will reduce key risks and make the identification of adaptation and mitigation strategies easier. An additional advantage of the framework is that it is not necessarily limited to Arctic coastal situations. We are certain of its wider applicability and look forward to adapting it to other spatial and social contexts, where local risk assessments are desired.

3. Methods

The data collection, analysis and synthesis presented in this report was carried out collaboratively by a multidisciplinary group of researchers from the disciplines of various social sciences, health sciences and civil engineering whose members have collectively conducted interdisciplinary fieldwork with a focus on risks of permafrost thaw in four regions of study, namely, Ilulissat, West Greenland; Longyearbyen, Svalbard; Northernmost area of Sakha, Russia; and Aklavik, Inuvik and Tuktoyaktuk by the Beaufort Sea, Yukon coast and Mackenzie river delta, Canada. Interdisciplinary work is necessary when we look at big and complex questions on climate change – in this case permafrost thaw – and the impacts on human society with a focus on issues and problems that are cross-sectoral and of wide scope. Complex issues of this magnitude raise questions that cannot meaningfully be resolved by relying on

insights from just one disciplines, but rather it requires the contributions of experts from many fields, including local experts and Indigenous and local knowledge.

Premised on the notion of the dual dimension of risk, as both physically and socially constructed, as well as the need to place risk perception and the coproduction of risk management with local stakeholders into any framework for understanding risks from climate change (see above), the researchers conducted participant observation and engaged in a broad range of community consultations specifically aimed at facilitating the identification of risks of thawing permafrost in close collaboration between local communities and scientists. Following and in conjunction with the reviewing of normative, narrative, and academic literature, as well engaging in workshops – some of which included the participation and input from natural and physical scientists within the Nunataryuk consortium – original interview and observation data was gathered from both a series of intensive ethnographic fieldwork seasons and long-term ethnographic fieldwork during which a broad range of local stakeholders and experts were consulted. Fieldwork methods, settings and sessions included pre-planned and ad hoc workshops; townhall meetings; heterogeneous and homogeneous focus groups; visits to and discussions in various workplaces, offices, businesses, and other institutions; semi-structured, unstructured (open-ended) and structured interviews, in-dept and narrative individual interviews, a survey, participant observation and informal conversations.

4. Five key hazards of permafrost thaw: A generalized risk analysis

4.1. Process

Work Package 9 (Adaptation and Mitigation) in collaboration with work packages 5 (Health and Pollution), 6 (Coastal Infrastructure) and 7 (Natural Resources, Economy & Coastal Community Planning) developed a risk analysis framework (Larsen et al. 2021), which is guiding our analysis of risks related to permafrost thaw in four study areas: Tiksi and Bykovskiy in Russia, the Avannaata Region in Greenland, the Beaufort Sea and Mackenzie River Delta Region in Canada, and Svalbard, Norway. The following is a broad illustration of the different process components throughout the project duration:

The aim of this risk analysis was to bring together knowledge produced with different methods, in different fields, within the different work packages. Data for the risk analysis was gathered by scientists from all work packages and then collected during two risk workshops – one at a Nunataryuk General Assembly in 2019 and one during an online General Assembly meeting using ‘Mural’ in 2021. During the 2019 workshop all present Nunataryuk scientists were grouped according to their respective work packages and asked to 1) define risks, including uncertainties, concern to humans, locality, definitions of risk and provide other comments identified within their work package. 2) Risks were then discussed in regional break-out groups (Nordic – Svalbard and Greenland, Beaufort Sea and East Siberia) as well as within a panel group discussion among scientists and local stakeholders. During the Mural exercise in 2021 Nunataryuk scientists, again grouped in to work packages, where asked to 1) verify direct geo-physical key risks 2) identify indirect risks and 3) identify feasibly measurable risks.

4.2. Five Key Hazards

The compounded data was then sorted and analyzed in collaboration with engineering scientists from WP6. Through this process we identified **five key hazards** in relation to permafrost thaw which are: infrastructure failure, disruption of mobility and supplies, decrease in water quality, challenges for food security and exposure to infectious diseases and contaminants.

Infrastructure failure: Arctic communities heavily rely on the services provided by their housing, communication, transport and energy infrastructures. Yet, permafrost thaw and coastal erosion frequently threaten the integrity of the built environment.

Disruption of mobility and supplies: Permafrost thaw causes structural damages to transportation infrastructure, and food and water supply facilities. Extreme weather events and changes in erosion patterns additionally disrupt navigation routes, reducing mobility and access to resources.

Five Key Hazards from Permafrost Thaw in Arctic Coastal Communities

Decrease in water quality: In permafrost regions, erosion, hydrological processes and human actions cause the release of nutrients, sediments and contaminants into aquatic systems. The

deterioration of fresh and saline water quality deeply affects ecosystems, subsistence and clean water supply.

Challenges for food security: *Losses of biodiversity, species habitats and population sizes constitute challenges for subsistence activities. Infrastructure failures and disruption of travel routes moreover affect food quality and supplies through the release of pollutants, diseases and reduction in access.*

Exposure to infectious diseases and contaminants: *Permafrost thaw and erosion cause the diffusion of mercury, and of existing and ancient infectious diseases. Unsecured hazardous waste increases exposure to contaminants. The development of harmful algae blooms constitutes a threat to living water organisms.*

4.3. Definitions

Further, we identified 1) Key physical **processes/drivers** which lead to physical, chemical and biological impacts that 2) create the above-mentioned **hazards**. These in turn have 3) direct and indirect (perceived) **consequences for various spheres of human lives**, which change /feedback on human **perceptions**. These physical impacts, hazards, consequences and perceptions then can create the need to implement 4) **adaptation and mitigation measures**.

We used the following definitions in this process:

- **RISK:** Measure of probability of occurrence of harmful event/danger, severity of consequences caused by the adverse effects on humans and the ecosystem, and perception of risk.
- **HAZARD:** Associated to probability that danger/harmful event occurs within a given period of time / Source of potential harm to humans and the ecosystem.
- **CONSEQUENCES:** Associated to the definition of risk which is expressed as frequency of harmful event X severity of associated consequences, etc., BUT often assimilated to impacts and/or generated costs.
- **IMPACTS:** Something logistically or naturally following from an action and/or conditions related to physical processes from climate change/variability.
- **RISK PERCEPTION:** Significance assigned to risks by stakeholders, derived from their needs, issues/challenges and concerns.

4.4. Physical Drivers and (Perceived) Consequences

The key physical drivers were grouped as follows: 1) Changes in Climate & Weather Conditions, 2) Human Influences, 3) Terrestrial & Subsea Permafrost Degradation, 4) Soil Instabilities & Erosion, 5) Changes in Flora & Fauna, 6) Hydrological Changes, and 7) Changes in Cycles (Biological, Geological and Chemical). To illuminate, here are a few examples of these drivers:

- Human activities such as mining change the environment. Permafrost thaw needs to be considered with respect to related infrastructure as well as the potential release of contaminants, such as around old oil and gas wells in Northwest Canada or in Northern Russia.
- Even where permafrost is very cold like in North-East Siberia ground temperatures are increasing at higher rates than elsewhere across the Arctic.
- In West Greenland, ground is continuously subsiding in proximity of the built environment, for example only a few hundred meters from the Ilulissat airport. In 2017 a rock slide in the Karrat Fjord triggered a tsunami wave which hit the nearby village of Nuugaatsiaq with devastating impact.

The five key hazards have direct and indirect (perceived) consequences for various spheres of human lives such as:

- **CULTURE & LANGUAGE:** Increased permafrost thaw causes impacts on livelihoods and subsistence, heritage and identity, if, for example, food sources change and intergenerational knowledge transfer is threatened.
- **HEALTH & WELLBEING:** Impacts on physical and mental health and wellbeing include, for example, higher potentials for injuries and greater insecurity in terms of safe food consumption.
- **COSTS & ECONOMY:** Repairs and new equipment, a higher reliance on store-bought food, physical protective measures and other necessary adaptation measures financially impact communities, families and individuals.
- **ECOSYSTEM (FUNCTIONING):** Disruptions and changes, such as changing nutrient fluxes, bio-accumulation of mercury and outbreaks of anthrax disease, cause concerns about the normal functioning of ecosystems.
- **RECREATION & BEING IN NATURE:** Recreational activities and being in nature is adversely affected, for example, by changes in navigable water and terrestrial paths and more difficult access to camps.
- **PLANNING & FATE CONTROL:** Planning and fate control are impacted by, for example, the potential loss of connectivity and supply irregularities. The need for new water and food sources may arise.

Key Risks of Permafrost Thaw on Svalbard

- In the Mackenzie River Delta, Ryan has already lost a cabin, a diesel generator and a skidoo to sudden river bank erosion, all in the past few years.
- A lot of infrastructure in Russia is located near coastal areas in West Siberia (Yamal) in the current transition zone of permafrost, which will disappear in the near future. The dam of the water reservoir at Tiksi broke recently, probably due to discontinuation of (permafrost cooling) maintenance measures.
- Between 2018 and 2020, road repairs and maintenance operations conducted in the Avannaata municipality in Greenland have resulted in many unforeseen expenditures and costs.
- On Svalbard, cultural heritage such as trappers' cabins or remnants from the mining industry are at risk of being destroyed by thawing permafrost, as foundations subside and rot.

Following this classification, we verified all consequences and related perceptions for each of our study sites. The following chart shows results for *Infrastructure Failure* in Northwest Greenland (Avannaata Municipality), for example:

Perceived Consequences of Infrastructure Failure related to Permafrost Thaw in Avannaata Municipality, Greenland

4.1. Risks Diagram

It must be noted that perceptions of risks and adaptation strategies in different field sites vary depending on local permafrost extent, characteristics and geological profiles, and many other factors such as:

- Transience/rootedness/sense of place and cultural backgrounds
- Livelihood, occupation and educational attainment
- Socio-economic situation and governance structures
- Personal (religious, political etc.) belief, and value orientations
- Knowledge Base and Transfer as well as levels of integration of different types of knowledge

- Presence or absence of climate change discourse and environmental consciousness
- Built environment and types of surrounding landscapes
- Past experiences (individual & collective) and (colonial, local) Histories

However, In order to give a generalized overview for a lay public audience of risks related to permafrost thaw in Arctic coastal areas, we are developing a risk diagram, which will appear in the Atlas of Permafrost in 2023. For more information on the creation of this Atlas visit: <https://nunataryuk.org/news/atlas>

The following is a preliminary version of this risk diagram based on the input we have gathered so far. It includes adaptation and mitigation measures, which were classified as belonging to either one or more of the following nine groups: 1) Financial Investments, 2) Construction Measures, 3) Modification of Technology & Communication Means; 4) Modification of Mobility Patterns, 5) Adaptation of & Investment in Training, Education & Capacity, 6) Modification of Energy, Food And Water Provision Practices, 7) Modification of Regulatory & Planning Frameworks & Policies, 8) Monitoring, Testing, Purifying & Regulating Practices, and finally 9) GHG and other Contaminant Emission Reduction.

Examples of Adaptation Practices in Nunataryuk Study Sites

- The Greenland government is working on implementing standards and norms (the National Annexes for the Eurocodes) to provide an up-to-date and adequate regulatory framework for buildings and constructions.
- North West Canada and Greenland are actively investing in renewable energy, such as wind, hydro and solar power, to reduce carbon footprint.
- On Svalbard new buildings and structures are built with foundations better adapted to a thawing ground, e.g. steel piles that are drilled deeper into the permafrost. Further, measures for protecting infrastructure below landslide prone slopes have been taken.
- In Inuvik, experimental pilings and ground temperature monitors are used to test best practices in preserving the permafrost below buildings and maintaining structural stability.

The **Risk Diagram** will be revised following risk workshops in three study sites (Inuvik, Ilulissat and Longyearbyen). The diagram shows that permafrost thaw across the Arctic coast poses a variety of key hazards to local and Indigenous lifeways including infrastructure failure, disruption of mobility and supplies, a potential decrease in water quality, challenges for food security and exposure to infectious diseases and contaminants – in addition to having a significant impact on the global climate. These key hazards (center) are caused by physical drivers (left), they have significant environmental, socio-cultural, economic and health-related perceived impacts on Arctic communities (right) and they necessitate a variety of adaptation and recovery measures (bottom).

Key Risks from Permafrost Thaw in Nunataryuk Study Sites

4.2. Conclusion

The information represented in the graphics shown in this section were produced based on data collection over several years from the Avannaata municipality in Northwestern Greenland, the Tiksi and Bykovskiy area in North-Eastern Siberia, from Svalbard, Norway, and from the Beaufort Sea Region in North-Western Canada (see also the section on methods). We employed a mixed-methods, interdisciplinary approach, which included the health, engineering, social as well as natural sciences. The time and spatial scales reflect those of impacted communities. The risk diagram especially thus paints a very generalized picture, while in fact many of the aspects of permafrost thaw described here are highly place and context-dependent. The following section delves into greater detail for four of our study sites: Svalbard in Northern Norway, the Mackenzie River Delta and Beaufort Sea Region in Northwest Canada, Tiksi and Bykovskiy in the Republic of Sakha in Northeast Russia as well as Ilulissat in West Greenland.

5. Case studies

5.1. Ilulissat, West Greenland

5.1.1. Summary

To many local residents in Ilulissat permafrost thaw is considered a challenge to one or more of the central quality of life domains, including infrastructure, economy and planning, and fate control. At the same time, results suggest that the extent of this challenge is perceived to be larger than it otherwise might have been if it wasn't for a lack of financial resources, the need for prioritization within the public and private sectors and the associated critical trade-offs; a perceived lack of effective planning by public and private sectors; and the well-known yet complex interactions of multiple factors, including other climate factors (Larsen et al., in prep).

5.1.2. Case study site description

With a population of nearly 5000 inhabitants and 3200 sled dogs, Ilulissat (69°13'N 51°06'W), formerly known as Jakobshavn, is the third largest town in Greenland. Located on the coast of Disko Bay in western Greenland, Ilulissat is the administrative and main service centre of Avannaata municipality, which was created in 2018 and encompasses more than 522 thousand square km, extending northward to the Nares Strait at 80 degrees north latitude. Avannaata includes four towns - Qaanaaq, Upernavik, Ummannaq and Ilulissat – and 23 villages or small settlements. The backbone of the Ilulissat economy consists of fisheries and tourism, but these sectors together with public services and construction provide most employment. The fisheries fleet includes both trawlers and smaller ships and boats, while halibut and shrimp are the main species that are processed in the local factories which rely to a significant extent on foreign employees. Benefiting from the proximity of the UNESCO World Heritage ice fjord, the

settlement is particularly attractive for tourism development. Especially considering the ongoing construction of an international airport and an extended airstrip, a rapid increase in the number of residents, foreign employees, and tourists is expected. Therefore, there is a need for new and reliable facilities in the coming years for sustaining the development of the town.

As a further challenge, the town has been experiencing significant infrastructure issues, that can be attributed to climate change and permafrost degradation processes as well as inadequate construction work. Housing and linear infrastructure are being damaged by ground movements and permafrost degradation requiring constant and costly short-term repairs. Our local informants cite the practices of carrying out hurried low-cost construction without proper site investigation as a perennial problem. Rigorous quality control and assurance must be developed and maintained, especially in the light of a predicted rapid increase in the numbers of residents and visitors. A possible increase in economic activities during the next several years pose elevated challenges; the expanded construction of infrastructure must be appropriately adapted to climate change impacts, including new water pipes replacing the ones currently located in the area where the road to the airport will be built. On the one hand, long-term logistical planning and the improvement of both construction practices and infrastructure lifespans remain complex and bound by the lack of technical and financial resources.

5.1.3. Methods

Using qualitative methods as well as a mixed-method questionnaire survey, ethnographic fieldwork was carried out in Ilulissat by teams of researchers from the academic disciplines of health sciences, social sciences, and civil engineering in the period 2019-2022. Community consultation meetings, interviews and group-discussions were conducted alternately in Danish, English, Kalaallisut and Icelandic. All interviewees signed informed-consent forms, and all sessions were recorded and transcribed and then written up in English, while research teams members also took notes which were subsequently assembled. Hired local interpreters took part in all sessions that included individuals who preferred the use of Kalaallisut, and researchers who spoke Danish translated the content to other researchers in English.

Our broad range of community consultation involved a variety of formal and informal settings and close engagements and dialogues with Ilulissat residents and experts as a way of obtaining as many accounts and perspectives as possible, including different types of knowledge and experience, as well as to foster an open, transparent, and inclusive co-production of knowledge. Fieldwork methods included a large pre-planned workshop; a townhall meeting; several prearranged focus groups; numerous smaller workshops in various workplaces, offices, businesses and schools; numerous semi-structured interviews with one or several local, indigenous and expert individuals at a time; as well as participant observations and informal conversations – all of which contributed to enhancing our understanding and generating further questions and discussions.

In each of the settings time was set aside to explain our project, answer questions, and clarify key issues. The main consultation meeting was the invited workshop with city planners, government employees, technical experts, and private sector entrepreneurs, but this pre-planned workshop was organized and held in collaboration with city officials in 2019. In this

initial workshop – and in the town hall meeting and the numerous smaller workshops and focus groups that followed in 2019, 2021 and 2022 – the setting allowed for a dynamic dialogue and open discussion where a variety of issues, challenges, opinions, and perspectives from different experts were brought to the table. For obtaining more detailed information and addressing technical questions, problems, and remedies, this was followed by scheduled interviews and follow-up meetings with selected individuals as well as others suggested by participants in the workshop.

5.1.4. Results

Interview results show that perceived key risks from permafrost thaw are associated with all life domains (see Table below) but in particular with Infrastructure and built environment, Economy and material wellbeing, and Fate control and planning, whereas risks to other life domains such as Health and wellbeing, Water and food security, and Cultural wellbeing are less likely to be attributed specifically or solely to permafrost thaw. The Table below presents examples of interview quotes. In particular, municipality representatives, technical personnel, private contractors, and business owners emphasize permafrost challenges associated with infrastructure and the built environment, including destabilizing ground for construction, and increased demand for high rise buildings; more frequent need for road and other infrastructure repairs; worsening road conditions, including potholes and crooked roads; damage to housing, including cracks, and doors and windows that cannot close properly.

Many interviewees emphasized the persistent challenges with the roads and houses: e.g. “We see a lot of issues with the roads”, and “Sometimes the doors cannot close, like windows cannot close.” Others talked about the need for constant repairs, e.g. “In Ilulissat, one or two years ago we began to put another asphalt layer on the roads. Now, just one and a half year later, you can see new damage”. Moreover, the larger and unexpected work caused by the nature of permafrost is noted by many: e.g. “There was actually a couple of cases last year, where we thought we had hit bedrock, you know we thought we cleared to bedrock and I’m out there and I’m like ‘This looks like bedrock, it feels like bedrock, but it’s not.’ We had to go another (several more meters) down.”

Most interviewees from both the private and public sectors emphasize the risks to economy and material wellbeing. More common perceived risks include difficulty budgeting due to uncertainties; multiple and conflicting priorities; financial constraints, and critical trade-offs; insufficient financial resources to meet increasing costs and demand for repairs and renovations; higher costs of operating business, increased costs to consumers, and/or less surplus. One interviewee explained: “And it's more expensive to build because you must insulate everything and make sure that it has proper heating and plumbing. Things just becomes more expensive.” Like many others one interviewee emphasized the financial constraints: “We do not have access to that kind of money. We are repairing buildings just before they're collapsing”, and “We have no money to build. Much of our money goes into maintenance and repairs”, and “Sadly, it's all about money”. Some business owners emphasized how costs from persistent challenges with permafrost thaw affects business operations and ultimately consumer prices (Larsen et al., in prep)

A common concern was also expressed by many interviewees from both private and public sectors about the risks to fate control and planning, which include risks related to a perceived

lack of a common set of priorities between politicians, local planners, infrastructure experts and other holders of technical-environmental knowledge; lack of multiyear financial planning and strategy for building, maintaining, and repairing of infrastructure; risks related to the increased unknown, and a decreased sense of control. One interviewee explained: “An accident can happen if we underestimate how much our cargo weighs. Can the bridge take the stress? And what if it can’t and then it crashes? And not just the accident as it happens, but you could basically cut the north part of the city totally off from the south part.” A contractor talked about the uncertainty associated with permafrost, e.g. “Instead of going down from 6 to 18 meters we actually went down 22 meters.”

Another interviewee talked about the impact for planning and development: “There’s a big area just north of Ilulissat where there is bedrock and no permafrost. Developing it is all about money. It costs a lot of money to develop a new area which also includes sewer and water etc. The plan is there, it’s already made, but who can now come up with the money?” Interview results suggest only limited perceived risks related to the life domains of Culture and Recreation and being in Nature; Water and Food Security; Health and wellbeing; and Education and Knowledge. Perceived risks include: More frequent accidents; and risk of back injuries: e.g. “we had a few drivers with back issues”; and risks related to recruitment and retention, and loss of critical knowledge and technical experience (e.g. “Critical knowledge has been lost over the years. We have a high turnover in employees. Knowledge is lost.”) which creates challenges to effective adaptation and mitigation.

Challenges associated with complex interactions of multiple factors was a common theme, e.g. “So just a hunter going out there, shooting one of the lines or whatever, or just the weather, the weather change and so on, can affect it. As soon as you have a power cut there, then it's just a diesel power plant here, which has to be the main power provider then.” And as another local explained: “The number of cars here in town has more than doubled in less than five years. It also creates a lot of stress on the network.” Much concern was also expressed about the planning and budgeting challenges related to the more recent municipality restructuring which has meant that the most northern town of Qaanaaq is now included in Avannaata municipality: “Not long ago the municipality was changed. Qaanaaq is now part of this municipality. And obviously they have a lot more permafrost and challenges up there. So that has added responsibility; and therefore, money has become tighter.”

An airport is being built which will help support a more effective travel and transportation but also growth of tourism. But infrastructure challenges and the cost of maintenance and repair due to permafrost raises the question of when and how the town will be ready to meet the potential growth in demand for new and better infrastructure. As one interviewee explains: “Of course, there will be many positive effects of the new airport. But if we don’t look at the entire picture, rethink the city, then I am afraid that there can be many negative effects. Because as we say, build an airport, but what do we have for infrastructure? I think that we need people to rethink the entire picture here.” (Larsen, et al., In prep).

5.1.5. Summary of perceived key risks

	Key risks (perceived)	Interview quotes (Examples)
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<p>Infrastructure and built environment</p>	<p>Heavy weight on permafrost damaged infrastructure can cause collapse.</p> <p>Damage to housing, including cracks, and doors and windows that cannot close properly.</p> <p>Amount of sand needed on roads increases due to permafrost thaw, risking clogging of ventilation system, and thereby causing more thawing.</p> <p>Collapsing sewage and water lines, and damage to masts, light poles, and pipes.</p> <p>More frequent need for road and other infrastructure repairs.</p> <p>Destabilizing ground for construction, and increased demand for high rise buildings.</p> <p>Worsening road conditions, including pot holes and crooked roads.</p> <p>Insufficient machinery, technological resources and knowledge to meet demand.</p> <p>Failure to distinguish permafrost layer from bedrock.</p> <p>Increasingly confined space for infrastructure and residential construction.</p> <p>Risks to the built environment due to a deepening of the active layer and resulting infrastructural instabilities and failure.</p> <p>Residential construction made increasingly complicated.</p>	<p>„As it is now, at least what we can see is that the roads are especially crooked.“</p> <p>„For that building over there, it's critical and it's hitting its structural integrity in the sense that internally we estimate two years, then we have to pull it down.“</p> <p>„The potholes in the road can be a challenge.“</p> <p>„But we have a number of foundations for the masts where these are placed directly in permafrost. They are not on a solid rock, on the base rock. And we do see changes there. We do have a project right now.“</p> <p>„The permafrost is definitely an issue, structure wise, for our light poles and so on and the foundation, which normally has been rock solid back in time and suddenly it comes up and you don't have connection with a base rock and things start to sag and fall over and so on. That's an ongoing problem.“</p> <p>„Sometimes the doors cannot close, like windows cannot close.“</p> <p>„I got my new apartment in 2013. And then in the fall and spring, I could not close the door because there were changes.“</p> <p>„We see a lot of issues with the roads.“</p> <p>„In Ilulissat, one or two years ago we began to put another asphalt layer on the roads. Now, just one and a half year later, you can see new damage.“</p> <p>„There was actually a couple of cases last year, where we thought we had hit bedrock, you know we thought we cleared to bedrock and I'm out there and I'm like 'This looks like bedrock, it feels like bedrock, but it's not.' We had to go another (more meters) down.“ „They do not invest the money they should in maintenance so they're losing infrastructure also because of that.“</p> <p>„We do not have so much area to build in the future. So now they will begin to build higher.“</p>
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<p>Health and wellbeing -</p>	<p>Concern about quality of drinking water, and related sickness.</p> <p>Risk of back injuries.</p> <p>More frequent accidents.</p>	<p>„We have had a few drivers with back issues.“</p> <p>„Accidents happen frequently. Frequently. I would say once every other month we have an accident of some sort. Some of them are minor where we can just pull the truck up and others are catastrophic where the car is total.“</p> <p>„Last fiscal year we had an issue or we had an accident that luckily didn't harm anyone.“</p> <p>„We are going to make a new strategic plan soon and we will include input from hospital staff for example.“</p> <p>„The doors and windows cannot close again. But we wait till people say enough is enough. That's their wish. They want to stay because the apartments are rather good, and maybe they've lived there 30 years.“</p>
<p>Economy and material wellbeing</p>	<p>Lack of financial commitment due to budget constraint and lack of financial resources.</p> <p>Difficulty budgeting due to uncertainties, multiple and conflicting priorities, financial constraints, and critical trade-offs.</p> <p>Increasing costs of housing, infrastructure and other construction; more expensive building requirements, repairs, maintenance and new construction.</p> <p>Insufficient financial resources to meet increasing costs and demand for repairs and renovations.</p> <p>Higher costs of operating business, increased costs to consumers, and/or less surplus.</p> <p>Difficulties meeting financial requirements for public and private sectors.</p> <p>Increasing costs related to the construction of new foundations for existing structures.</p>	<p>„And for our transportation Department, it hits our operating costs quite a bit because we have above normal levels of maintenance costs. Every time a truck drives across a crooked road, it costs a lot more to maintain than if it drives on a straight road. It hits everything from suspension to the gear box. Everything breaks down faster, which means we have to compensate towards our customers in terms of higher prices. So that's one part.“</p> <p>„And it's more expensive to build because you have to insulate everything and make sure that it has proper heating and plumbing. Things just becomes more expensive.“</p> <p>„We do not have access to that kind of money. We are repairing buildings just before they're collapsing.“</p> <p>„And the stairs are broken down because of rot. We can't expect money because we have permafrost disappearing up here.“</p> <p>„It's just survival.“</p> <p>„We can't do all the things we want to but with the limited amount of money we have we are doing the best we can.“ „It's a question about money.“</p>

<p>Culture and recreation, being in nature</p>	<p>Concerns about ability to attend to cultural needs due to budget demand for other priorities related to permafrost.</p> <p>Concerns about ability to engage in cultural and recreational activities at the same level as earlier.</p>	<p>„Those activities we can no longer guarantee that you can experience in those months of the year.“</p> <p>„Dogsledding is increasingly a challenge.“</p>
<p>Water and food security</p>	<p>Risks related to freshwater supply.</p>	<p>„We have the water coming from the sea out here. We have that annually when the snow melts, we have a weird and grassy smell of the water. Sometimes we can get some stomach issues before they get some chlorine. But that's it.“</p>
<p>Fate control, including planning</p>	<p>Lack of common set of priorities between politicians, local planners, infrastructure experts and other holders of technical-environmental knowledge.</p> <p>Lack of multiyear financial planning and strategy for building, maintaining, and repairing of infrastructure.</p> <p>Insufficient financial resources to meet demands for maintenance and repair of municipality structures.</p> <p>Difficulty attracting and retaining sufficient - and timely - construction companies, technical resources, trades people and other experts.</p> <p>Risks to effective planning, the increased unknown, and reduced sense of control.</p> <p>Challenges in budgeting and decision making, and related critical trade-offs.</p>	<p>„An accident can happen if we underestimate how much our cargo weighs. Can the bridge take the stress? And what if it can't and then it crashes? And not just the accident as it happens, but you could basically cut the north part of the city totally off from the south part.“</p> <p>„Employees in the municipality stay here a few years and then they move on. It's very hard to have a good dialogue.“</p> <p>„Sadly, it's all about money. The project over here has been delayed because it should be cheaper.“</p> <p>„It's the cheapest developer who gets the development job. So that's also accumulating the risk of failures.“</p> <p>„Instead of going down from 6 to 18 m we actually went down 22 meters.“</p> <p>„We need to be prepared for unforeseen expenses.“</p> <p>„The need to prioritize creates challenges in budgeting given the climatic changes here.“</p> <p>„We have the detailed knowledge of the needs and possibilities for building and repairing infrastructure such as roads, houses, harbors, and schools and we make suggestions to municipal politicians, but the politicians make the budget for the year and fully decide what must be done, i.e., what projects we must accomplish.“</p>

		<p>„In Ilulissat there is not much space left: We are very restricted in the part where we have the UNESCO Heritage Site, we can't build anywhere towards that. We can't build really towards the airport. And we have this water block zone, where we get the freshwater, and we can't go there. And in between there is all these swampy areas. Therefore, where houses are built now is pretty much where you can build them.“</p> <p>„We have a huge maintenance problem with much of our large municipality's structures because we don't have enough money to maintain things.“</p>
<p>Education and knowledge</p>	<p>Risks from gaps in education and knowledge to meet growing challenge.</p> <p>Risks related to recruitment and retention, and loss of critical knowledge and technical experience.</p>	<p>„Critical knowledge has been lost during the years. We have a high turnover in employees. Knowledge is lost.“</p> <p>„The design engineers are not even in Denmark or here. They are in other parts of the world, but we meet via video conferencing. And a lot of the information is by digital format. And then explanation starts. Okay. What is this? What is that?“</p>
<p>Travel and transportation</p>	<p>Frequent damage complicates flow and stability of travel and transport.</p> <p>Challenges to getting timely resupply.</p> <p>Added stress of increased number of cars on permafrost affected ground.</p> <p>Increased movement of building material and more weight on destabilized infrastructure (bridges) and related damage and safety concerns.</p> <p>Choice of foundation material for runways and roads.</p> <p>Remoteness and challenges with supply of labour.</p>	<p>„One transport company actually have their own mechanics and stuff like that because they say that it's so hard on the vehicles up here that they need to have staff working on maintenance all the time. And also because if you need spare parts you don't have, like in Denmark, just drive to Aarhus or Copenhagen and get something sent and you have it the next day. Up here it's by ship from Denmark. It's like four weeks and by flight, even now, it's like 14 days for stuff like that.“</p> <p>„The number of cars here in town has more than doubled in less than five years. So it also creates a lot of stress on the network.“</p> <p>„In Ilulissat, one or two years ago we began to put another asphalt layer on the roads. Now, just one and a half year later, you can see new damage.“</p> <p>„We have a structural plan which includes building a harbour north of the airport. This requires much new infrastructure and reengineering of the narrow bridge. But we have</p>

		<p>decided not to think about it now. Because then we get a headache.”</p> <p>„So, the mere fact that we are building the foundation of the runway from rock instead of the normal soil constitution, it’s, what can I say, it’s mind boggling.“</p>
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5.1.6. Conclusion

The case of Ilulissat suggests based on extensive interview material collected over a period of three years that permafrost thaw poses risks to several life domains that are important to overall human wellbeing. At the same time, interview data also suggest that persistent and growing risks from permafrost thaw are the result of limited financial resources, and that solutions to overcome permafrost related risks include solving some major budget challenges. A general perception among local residents was that with sufficient financial resources permafrost would not pose a key risk to any of the life domains. Lack of financial resources necessitates prioritization which in turn leads to critical trade-offs and amplifies the negative impacts from thawing permafrost. Results suggest that more effective planning, better communication and coordination can reduce the risks from permafrost thaw (Larsen et al. (in prep)). Further, the results show that complex interactions between permafrost thaw and other societal factors result in key societal risks. Permafrost amplifies other existing challenges such as the housing shortage. As explained by one interviewee: “Creating new buildings is very expensive here and most homes are public housing. People are on the waiting list for years while staying with family or in a homeless center which we just finished building last year.” In general, the data collected suggest that what local residents emphasize and how they rate the risks from permafrost thaw depends on their role, responsibility, and general life situation. In addition, interviewees often remarked that they found it difficult to distinguish between different climate factors, e.g. one interviewee responded: “It is also hard for me to differentiate weather and climate change but I think we are very dependent on the weather and I feel a bit more out of control due to the weather as to what I can do.”

5.2. The Beaufort Sea Region, Yukon Coast and Mackenzie River Delta

5.2.1. Summary

The Canadian case study comprises four communities, located in the Northwest Territories, in or near the Mackenzie Delta, in Canada’s western Arctic. Along with an increase in air temperatures by more than two degrees Celsius between the mid 20th century and the year 2016 (Bush and Lemmen 2019), came more rain and humidity, lower snow and ice levels (Box et al. 2019), melting glaciers (Asong et al. 2020), changing winds (Wesche and Chan 2010) , and increased frequencies of storms (Ford et al. 2018) and flooding (Worden et al. 2020). Additionally, coastal and river bank erosion (Wesche and Chan 2010, Worden et al. 2020) and

subsidence and slumping (Irrgang et al. 2019, Lantz and Kokelj 2008, Lantz and Turner 2015, Ramage 2016) caused by permafrost thaw modify the home of the predominantly Inuvialuit and Gwich'in First Nation population, putting infrastructure, health and wellbeing, mobility, supply as well as food and water security at risk.

5.2.2. Case study site description

Aklavik is situated along the Peel Chanel within the Mackenzie Delta, approximately 100 km south of the Yukon Coast/Beaufort Sea. The community has a population of 536 inhabitants (Statistics Canada 2021), most of whom are Inuvialuit or Gwich'in First Nation citizens. Similar to most communities in the Canadian Arctic, Aklavik has a mixed subsistence-cash economy composed of wage employment and subsistence harvesting. Inuvik was conceived in 1953 as the administrative hub and service centre on the eastern edge of the Mackenzie River Delta Region. Lying on the border of the Gwich'in First Nation and Inuvialuit Settlement Region it was the home of 3137 people in the year 2021 (Statistics Canada 2021). Tuktoyaktuk, which means „it looks like a caribou“ in Inuvialuktun, is another of the six Inuvialuit hamlets in the Inuvialuit Settlement Region. „Tuk“ lies on the shore of the Arctic Ocean in the Kugmallit Bay, near the Mackenzie River Delta and is the terminus of the all-season Inuvik-Tuktoyaktuk Highway. The historical Inuvialuit dwelling place was home to 937 people in 2021 (Statistics Canada 2021) and experienced significant rates of shoreline erosion in past years. The majority of people living in FortMcPherson are Teet'it Gwich'in First Nation citizens. Sitting on the south side of the Mackenzie River Delta, on the east bank of the Peel River 121 km south of Inuvik, Fort McPherson is home to 647 people, speaking two principal languages: Gwich'in and English. The community is connected by road (the Dempster Highway) and like Aklavik and Tuktoyaktuk has a mixed economy of wage employment and subsistence harvesting.

5.2.3. Objective

As the stable layer of permafrost is increasingly deteriorating along the Yukon Coast and in the Mackenzie River Delta (Andrews et al. 2016, Burn and Kokelj 2009, Lantuit et al. 2012.) which is mostly consisting of accumulated mud from river sediments (Hill et al., 2001), the focus of the Canadian study has been to identify changes observed by Indigenous knowledge holders and active land users in relation to the thawing ground. Thanks to their highly mobile subsistence patterns, the latter are most knowledgeable of a wide range of changes occurring in the wider region and provide valuable insights and (long-term) observations stemming from an intimate and multi-generational knowledge of the land and it's inhabitants, as well as adaptation practices. The region is characterized by ubiquitous permafrost, the tree line that traverses the delta and thousands of rivers and lakes that are frozen for more than six months of the year. High levels of landscape and environmental changes cause various concerns for the Indigenous and non-Indigenous inhabitants, making constant and costly adaptation to ever increasing and accelerating landscape changes necessary.

5.2.4. Methods

In March 2019, one week of project introduction with multiple stakeholder engagement was conducted in Inuvik and Aklavik – notably with representatives of the Inuvialuit Regional Corporation and the Gwich'in Tribal Council. Between 2019 and 2022 online interviews, a literature review and (online and in-person) workshops with Nunataryuk scientists working in the field site as well as representatives of Indigenous organizations in Aklavik and Tuktoyaktuk were conducted. This was followed by 24 weeks of fieldwork starting mid-September 2022 (ongoing). During this period expert interviews were conducted with representatives of local organizations as well as with regional engineering, heritage and permafrost experts. Further, field visits took place to various sites along the Dempster highway, the Inuvik-Tuktoyaktuk Highway, and along the Mackenzie river channel connecting Inuvik and Aklavik. Finally, qualitative semi-structured life-history and land-use interviews with 24 Indigenous knowledge holders were conducted (in English, since all participants were fluent speakers). These interviews lasted on average 1 to 1.5 hours, with a relatively even distribution of genders (m=13, f=11), and higher representation of older age groups due to their accumulated knowledge of land changes: (20-40 = 3, m=2/f=1 // 40-60 = 11, m=6/f=5 // 60+ = 10m=5/f=5) in Aklavik (n=10), Fort McPherson (n=6), Tuktoyaktuk (n=3) and Inuvik (n=5).

5.2.5. Results

Increased permafrost thaw is largely considered having a negative impact on life in the Beaufort Sea Region and the Mackenzie River Delta (Ramage et al. 2022). Infrastructure failure is a main concern, such as cabins that are increasingly threatened to or actually falling in to the water near coasts and river banks: „I got a cabin 70 kilometers out from Inuvik. And in the last two years I lost over 30 feet of land. And you know, I had nice trees there, I thought that'll help keep it intact, but it didn't.“ Concerns for health are voiced too (see also Timlin et al. 2022a), such as for injuries or additional strains on mental and physical health caused by changes and the need for adaptation: „I have a camp on the river, it's about 50 kilometers from Inuvik. Just this summer a big chunk of land right next to my cabin came off and fell in to the river. We went back out to my cabin and it was gone.“ Health concerns arise caused by the situation itself as well as the additional efforts needed to adapt: “It's lots of work to try and adapt. It's lots of work to try and try and live off the land.” Adaptation costs created by damages to roads, airstrips, cabins, houses etc. put an additional strain on individual and communal financial security.

Culture and heritage are seen at risk, such as when it comes to the loss and/or maintenance of historical heritage sites (Andrews et al. 2016, Friesen 2015, Hollesen 2018). Cultural vitality and subsistence are negatively affected when time and resources are taken away by necessary adaptation measures: „We couldn't really do anything (hunting, trapping or fishing) this summer because all we had to focus on is: Okay, our (river) banks are falling too much, we have to try and get the small house moved back. It's scary.“ Since subsistence harvesting plays such a pivotal role in cultural vitality and for food security it is seen as a major area of concern: „I ask myself, how is our subsistence harvest being affected by permafrost thaw? If our subsistence harvest is going to be endangered by climate change, then we have to start working on protecting those rights and the animals.“ Planning needs to be adapted to changing circumstances, whereas the acceleration of change poses a challenge to fate control; people feel that there is nothing they can do about the developments and that they have no choice but to keep adapting: „Our land is eroding right in front of us. I don't know what we could do.

You know, we're high up in the Arctic where it's supposed to be freezing all the time. And it's not. Everything is changing and you have to learn to adapt to it. We have no choice, right? We got to try and figure out ways of how to live like this.“

Brushes, especially willows, grow thicker and higher, making it harder to move across the land as well as providing better cover for moose for example, an important country food. At the same time the ground and vegetation has become softer during the warm period of the year making it harder to walk across the tundra for example while berry picking, while walking across the land means increasingly disturbing the ground and vegetation. „We never used to have any brush, right? Because the ground was always frozen. Now there's brush everywhere. There's willows and thick brush all over. And it grows in no time now, because our summers are so hot. Sometime moose run into the willows and hunters can't follow them.“ Finally, increased permafrost thaw creates challenges in regards to mobility and travel: “The erosion in rivers is changing our travelling routes, they are getting longer, parts of the river that were deep before are now almost dried out, and traditional hunting grounds are harder to get to. My kids or grandkids might not even have access to the places we used to go to.”

5.2.1. Summary of perceived key risks

	Key risks (perceived)	Interview quotes (Examples) – all quotes are by Inuvialuit or Gwich'in First Nation Land Users and Knowledge Holders
Infrastructure	Infrastructure failure, such as houses and cabins that are increasingly threatened to or actually falling in to the water near coasts and river banks.	„I have a camp on the river, it's about 50 kilometers from Inuvik. Just this summer, maybe, end of July a big chunk of land right next to my cabin came off and fell in to the river. We went back out to my cabin and it was gone. I was scared to go around the corner and see if my camp was still there! Because it's like 300 feet wide, and like 100 feet inland, it's gone.“
Health and wellbeing	Concerns for injuries or loss of lives, and additional strains on health caused by changes and the need for adaptation. Mental Health concerns caused by the situation itself as well as the additional efforts needed to adapt.	“So, I moved my house back. Got it releveled. And I built an extension hoping that -- but is that enough? Like, should I cut more brush? And move it more back? It's nerve wrecking, you know!” „And I cut lots of brush. And even that's lots of work, especially when it's summertime when it's so hot out. But we have to do it, it's got to work because nobody else is going to do it for you.“ “I sure hope it doesn't take a massive amount of landslides, mass amount of deaths that might happen from it, in order for the world to listen.”
Economy and material wellbeing	Costs created by damages to roads, airstrips, cabins, houses etc. put an additional strain on individual and communal financial security	“It's lots of work to try and adapt. It's lots of work to try and try and live off the land. The land is expensive.” „I spend so much money on buying supplies for my house. Our wood prices up here, our

		plywood and all that is outrageous. Because of COVID all the wood prices went up.“
Culture and Language	Concerns for the loss and/or maintenance of cultural, tangible and intangible heritage and concern for cultural vitality, which is negatively affected because time and resources are taken away by necessary adaptation measures.	„We couldn't really do anything (hunting, trapping or fishing) because all we had to focus on is: Okay, our (river) banks are falling too much, we have to try and get the small house moved back, because we lost - what is it - two or three trees in front of the house! They just fell over because the ground is just too soft for the tree to be there, so they fell over. So that scares me, like what if the one of those trees falls on the house?“
Water and food security	Subsistence is negatively affected because time and resources are taken away by necessary adaptation measures.	„Last time we went hunting we had to take a longer route to avoid a large area where there was slumping.“
Fate control, including planning	Planning needs to be adapted to changing circumstances. Acceleration of change poses a challenge to fate control, people feel that there is no choice but to adapt and that there is nothing they can do about the developments.	„I love it here and that's why we live up here, and we want it to be cold. We want the ground to be frozen when it's supposed to be frozen.“ „We can't change what's happening, we just need to adapt.“ „I lost several feet of shore in front of my house just this year, but I like it where my house is now, I don't want to move.“
Recreation and Being in nature	Brushes grow thicker and higher, making it harder to move across the land. The ground and vegetation has become softer making it harder to walk across the tundra. Time for recreation is taken away by necessary adaptation measures.	„But now, you can see the ground thawing, you can see where there never used to be brush, like willows and all that stuff. It's all full grown now, because of the ground that's thawing.“ „In the past few years I already had to winch back my cabin three times!“ „It's so much work, we need more money and manpower to adapt.“
Travel and transportation (Mobility & Supply)	Travel routes across the land and waters change due to erosion and slumping, travel becomes more unpredictable and dangerous. Road damage can interrupt access to camps and recreational sites.	„Climate change and permafrost thaw changes the landscape, it changes your waterways – like those channels on the west side of the Delta have changed with climate change, there is shallower water, it is hard to read, you can't navigate no more.“

5.2.2. Conclusion

In fact, permafrost thaw is just one small part in a bigger picture of many climate-related changes, a fact that is readily acknowledged by inhabitants of the Inuvialuit Settlement Region and the traditional territories of the local Gwich'in First Nations. The permafrost system includes multiple components that interact and trigger positive and negative feedback loops, regulating the state of permafrost. Human actions, changes in climate, landscape characteristics, and soil properties modify the permafrost equilibrium and may result in the occurrence of hazards, as described here. Just as physical drivers, (scientifically proven) consequences and (everyday) perceptions, grounded in long-term empirical observations and deep ecological knowledge are 1) sometimes difficult to differentiate and are 2) often closely interrelated with each other. Moreover, cultural lifeways and heritage are closely linked to aspects of health, subsistence and the built environment (amongst others). Many differences exist in addition not only between the communities that were part of this case study but also within individual perceptions. For example, it makes a difference if a person has just recently lost a cabin to erosion or if someone has not experienced any comparable major challenges in recent times – and the analysis presented here thus represents only a general overview.

5.3. Svalbard/Longyearbyen

5.3.1. Summary

Longyearbyen, Svalbard, is a community undergoing drastic environmental and socio-economic changes. Although permafrost thaw is not a matter of utmost concern to most locals, people in Longyearbyen are aware of thawing permafrost and associate it with negative changes. The main risk associated with permafrost thaw that people talk about, is risks to the built environment, i.e. infrastructure, housing and other buildings, and material cultural heritage. Furthermore, people in Longyearbyen relate permafrost thaw to challenges associated with changes in the physical environment, like landslides, mudslides, avalanches, and erosion.

5.3.2. Case study site description

Longyearbyen is located on the Western coast of the high-Arctic archipelago of Svalbard, part of the Kingdom of Norway. Svalbard never had an indigenous population, and its settlements developed as coal mining towns. Longyearbyen (ca. 2600 inhabitants) is the archipelago's largest settlement. And its administrative center. The former coal mining company town is at the tail end of an economic restructuring, and tourism and the related service industry, in addition to research and higher education, constitute its main economic pillars today (Sokolickova, Meyer, & Vlachov 2022). Longyearbyen is a highly modern, "urban village", at the same time geographically remote and well-connected to the Norwegian mainland via its airport. Its population is transient, young and increasingly international, with around 30% of the population from outside Norway.

Svalbard is experiencing severe climatic changes (Hanssen-Bauer et al. 2019): temperatures have risen 4 degrees celcius since 1971, which is five times faster than the global average. Permafrost temperatures on Svalbard have increased in recent years, and an increase of the active layer has been observed at some sites (Hanssen-Bauer et al. 2019). Under high emission scenarios, near-surface permafrost in coastal and low-lying areas is projected to thaw before the end of the century (Hanssen-Bauer et al. 2019). The recently published climate profile for Longyearbyen (Norsk Klimaservicesenter, 2019) projects that air temperature will continue to increase, as will annual precipitation. Thawing of the upper layers of permafrost is expected, as are more frequent events with strong precipitation, and more rain in winter. Increased precipitation and snow and glacier melt will result in more flooding, and river and coastal erosion are predicted. There will furthermore be an increase in snow and slush avalanches in coming years, and a thicker active permafrost layer in combination with more frequent rain events result in unstable slopes, increasing the risk for landslides and debris flows. Longyearbyen is often depicted as either a climate change victim or a showcase of technological solutions in the face of change (Meyer & Sokolickova, in prep.): in response to natural hazards such as snow avalanches, land slides, and infrastructural challenges due to permafrost thaw and coastal erosion, the town is adapting by producing environmental knowledge, reconfiguring the urban landscape, and developing technical protection measures.

5.3.3. Objective

Risks related to permafrost thaw were addressed throughout the research in relation to broader climate change impacts and societal transformations. The main focus was on perceived risks, thus understanding risk perception qualitatively – hence subjectively and contingent on societal contexts – as opposed to quantitative risk assessments.

The aim of the research was to understand how climate change – including permafrost thaw – is impacting the town of Longyearbyen, how people perceive, experience and live with the changes, and how they deal with them. Acknowledging that the social impacts of climate change are always contingent on specific local and societal contexts, the research from the outset addressed climate change and in particular permafrost thaw in the context of the social and economic restructuring that Longyearbyen is currently undergoing. While we were primarily interested in impacts, perceptions, and adaptations of climate change and thawing permafrost, it became clear very soon that these environmental changes are intertwined with societal issues, and that climate change is often not considered the most pressing issue locally.

In the course of the research, different thematic foci were explored. As the built environment is one main interface between climate, environment, and society, we explored how the town developed and why, and which challenges exist in urban development and planning today (Meyer 2022a). In a collaborative project between the local architecture office LPO arkitekter and the Svalbard Social Science Initiative, we investigated how people living in Longyearbyen perceive and use the town, and how they would like to see it develop in the future. A related focus was on perceived societal impacts and risks of climate change and permafrost thaw in Longyearbyen, and how experienced and projected impacts are dealt with locally. Both adaptation practices and meanings were examined (Meyer 2022b). Perceptions of climate change and thawing permafrost were addressed in conversations as well in the community survey (Ramage et al. 2022; Meyer & Sokolickova, in prep.). A recently added thematic focus

which developed out of local concerns and possibilities for interdisciplinary collaboration is on permafrost thaw impacts on cultural heritage, and related values and challenges connected to heritage conservation (Sinitsyn, Westermann, Arlov, et al. 2022).

5.3.4. Methods

The data for Longyearbyen have been collected through long-term ethnographic fieldwork: 17 months over the course of four years (2019-2022). During this time, the researcher took part in the town's life, engaged in numerous informal conversations and built relationships, and conducted more than 80 audio-recorded meetings in the form of formal expert, semi-structured and narrative interviews, and focus groups. The aim was to get a heterogeneous and representative sample, including people that could be labelled as "experts" regarding climate change and adaptation (planners, architects, engineers, etc.), "stakeholders" (representatives from the various sectors such as the local municipality, the tourist industry, etc.), and stakeholders in a wider sense meaning inhabitants and also visitors. The interviews and focus groups focused on the multiple changes (physical, social, economic) that Longyearbyen is undergoing. Permafrost thaw and related challenges were thus addressed in the context of multiple stressors (Räsänen et al., 2016). In addition, a community survey was conducted in Longyearbyen, Aklavik (Canada) and Qeqertarsuaq (Greenland), focusing on peoples' perceptions of permafrost thaw impacts. In Longyearbyen, a total of 84 responses were gathered between August 2019 and January 2020.

5.3.5. Results

In general, people in Longyearbyen associate permafrost thaw with negative changes. "Thawing permafrost is important – it is about dwelling and living here on Svalbard." By emphasizing living and dwelling, this quote from the community survey is illustrative of a key finding: that the main perceived societal impacts of permafrost thaw in Longyearbyen are its impacts on the built environment. The key risk people associate with permafrost thaw are its adverse impacts on housing, buildings and infrastructure, in terms of damages through natural hazards, sinking, subsidence, and in general instabilities. This risk is directly associated with climate change: "Climate change leads to movement in buildings, unstable piles, avalanches, landslides, at some places it is more difficult to move in nature." In addition to dwellings and infrastructure at risk, a main concern is the risk of loss of cultural heritage, such as remnants from the coal mining industry or trappers' cabins. As several interview partners emphasized, risks to the built environment are not a result of permafrost thaw alone, but of a combination of environmental factors and engineering practices and bad maintenance. These risk are furthermore considered an engineering challenge that can be dealt with. Another main sub-category of risk related to permafrost thaw in Longyearbyen are environmental risks, i.e. challenges associated with changes in the physical environment, most notably landslides and avalanches. These risks are by many associated with safety problems. One participant described the situation in Longyearbyen as people living "with a constant risk for natural hazard". Another participant expressed awareness of risks, but also the acceptance of the risk (for now): "We used to live beyond Sukkertoppen [a steep mountain with avalanche-prone

slopes]. We heard about the mudslides, but we lived there anyway. Now there is a new rule that you cannot build where there has been avalanches. If we think that it becomes too dangerous to live here, we will have to move. But we like it so much here that we don't want to move.” In this and another quote, the participants used the words “danger” and “dangerous” to describe a situation related to climate change and permafrost thaw. In both cases, the dangers were related to environmental risks (soil processes: mudslides, eroding hillsides). Many participants talked about the avalanches when asked about risks related to permafrost thaw: “Avalanche risk is a huge issue in our community. Because there is more rain and warmer temperatures, there is a higher risk for landslides in town. Outside of town we have cabins that were destroyed because of avalanches and landslides. [...] I think the main impact on health is on psychical health, when people live with a constant risk for natural hazard, and some are traumatized by the avalanches that hit town.”, but also coastal erosion and other environmental impacts: “On Vestpynten, it [thawing permafrost] has led to coastal erosion. Also it leads to the release of bacteria and old viruses, and to the release of methane.” The last two quotes furthermore point to another perceived risk related to permafrost thaw: risks to human and animal health. In addition to physical risks as a result of landslides, the release of contaminants due to permafrost thaw is considered a challenge. In this regard, some research participants expressed concerns regarding the impacts of permafrost thaw on fresh-water supply.

Many participants emphasized that permafrost thaw does not cause problems to them personally, a finding that was confirmed in the survey. One participant expressed it like this: “Everything is becoming more uncertain. There is more risk for landslides. The snow mobile season is becoming shorter due to climate change, this is something that affects me personally, but permafrost thaw is not really having an impact on my activities in the environment around Svalbard.” Permafrost thaw is thus by most participants perceived as a societal rather than a personal risk. Finally, it is important to note that permafrost thaw is a phenomenon difficult to understand for most non-experts, especially as the perceivable changes are happening very slowly. Also, permafrost thaw is not the change that seems most pressing to most people in Longyearbyen in a time of drastic societal and climatic changes. One participant expressed it in the following way: “Permafrost thaw is not something that I go around and think about. I know that permafrost may be a challenges for hunting, since you are not allowed to drive a four-wheeler on the tundra. But not sure if this has anything to do with permafrost thaw. I know that the community is having some trouble with permafrost because all the cable have to be above ground, but also here I'm not sure what the thawing has to do with it.”

5.3.1. Summary of perceived key risks

	Key risks (perceived)	Interview quotes (Examples)
Infrastructure	Risks to infrastructure and buildings from landslides and avalanches Infrastructure failure due to subsidence and instabilities	“Thawing permafrost is a challenge for houses on Svalbard.”; “The main problem is in regard to buildings and infrastructure, as the buildings move and destabilize when the permafrost thaws.”

	<p>Coastal erosion, posing risks to roads, cabins, and cultural heritage located along the shore</p> <p>Risk of loss of historical infrastructure and cultural heritage</p>	<p>“We used to live beyond <i>Sukkertoppen</i> [a steep mountain with avalanche-prone slopes]. We heard about the mudslides, but we lived there anyway. Now there is a new rule that you cannot build where there has been avalanches. If we think that it becomes too dangerous to live here, we will have to move. But we like it so much here that we don't want to move.”</p> <p>“Coastal erosion is also something that very much affects the planning area. It is the permafrost that holds the masses together. We saw in 2016 that a big part of <i>Bjørndalsveien</i> slid out.”</p> <p>“In the next big storm, <i>Taubanestasjonen</i> [a coal distribution structure classified as cultural heritage] in Hiorthhamn might fall down and go on the sea.”</p>
Health and wellbeing	<p>Physical risks related to natural hazards, such as landslides and avalanches</p> <p>Risks related to contamination in the ground that releases as permafrost thaws</p> <p>Mental health risks related to living with environmental changes and risks</p>	<p>“There are many old sins in Longyearbyen, in the form of waste disposal sites and pollution. It can be pollution that is held together by the frost, and that may come out if things start to thaw.”</p> <p>“I think the main impact on health is on psychological health, when people live with a constant risk for natural hazard, and some are traumatized by the avalanches that hit town.”</p>
Economy and material wellbeing	<p>Increasing costs for maintenance of buildings and infrastructure</p> <p>Increasing costs related to the construction of new foundations for existing structures</p>	<p>“Most can be solved, but it is the costs, it is expensive, it is very expensive.”</p>
Culture and recreation	<p>Exposure to natural hazards while being in nature (landslides, mudslides)</p>	<p>“When I'm out hunting, it is difficult to walk because of the deeper active layer, we sink into the ground.”</p>
Water and food security	<p>Risks of contamination and loss of the freshwater source <i>Isdammen</i>, as the dam that contains it might thaw</p>	<p>Expressed concern for the local freshwater reserve, <i>Isdammen</i>, “the ice dam”, literally dammed up by a road: “The problem is that when the permafrost disappears, the dam also</p>

		disappears, because it is the permafrost that holds it together”
Fate control, including planning	<p>Risks to the built environment due to natural hazards (soil processes such as mudslides and landslides) which impact urban development and planning</p> <p>Uncertainties related to future environmental conditions create challenges for planning</p> <p>Risks to the built environment due to a deepening of the active layer and resulting infrastructural instabilities and failure</p>	<p>“This is another consequence of ignoring environmental change, then you have fear in society. You have a local population that is afraid. And then you have a huge challenge. [...] If the government does not acknowledge this we will have big consequences. [...] And all of a sudden there is something that makes the city unattractive. People seek safety and if you don’t have safety, you don’t have people. And that is a huge consequence of climate change. [...] So what I’m saying is that the government needs to take climate change seriously and they need to be able to adapt.”</p> <p>“The guiding principle behind much urban development is to get people out of the avalanche zones.”.</p> <p>“There is great uncertainty in knowledge that we used to rely on. [...] So climate change challenges us quite a lot, because it changes the conditions.”</p>
Being in nature	Exposure to natural hazards while being in nature (landslides, mudslides)	“One of our favorite hikes, up to <i>Sarkofagen</i> , has become much more dangerous because of the eroding hillsides. There have been several landslides there so the trail is different now than before.”
Travel and transportation	<p>A road to the North-West of town has been partly destroyed by coastal erosion</p> <p>Roads are at risk from soil processes and subsidence and have to be temporarily closed for safety reasons</p> <p>The airport strip is bumpy and at risk from subsidence</p>	“Coastal erosion is also something that very much affects the planning area. It is the permafrost that holds the masses together. We saw in 2016 that a big part of <i>Bjørndalsveien</i> slid out.”

5.3.2. Conclusion

Whereas in the other study areas permafrost thaw is considered a challenge in all life domains, in Longyearbyen the main perceived risks are those related to the natural and built environment. Problems in the realms of politics, happiness, health, food storage and work are hardly associated with permafrost thaw, and spiritual and religious problems are considered completely unaffected by permafrost thaw. Given that risk perception is always dependent on specific societal and cultural contexts, this main finding may indicate that the predominantly Western worldview of Longyearbyen's non-indigenous inhabitants, as well as a lifestyle and economy not dependent on subsistence activities, results in a perception of risk as something predominantly physical, impacting society via the built and natural environment. Furthermore, risk perception in the realm of environmental changes is in Longyearbyen deeply intertwined with the traumatic experience of two major avalanches destroying houses in 2015 and 2017, the former killing two people, events that have been widely ascribed to climate change.

A peculiar notion that came up several times during fieldwork in Longyearbyen, is the difference in risk perception between permafrost "non-experts" and "experts" (like engineers, scientists, and architects), but also between experts. The interview data as well as debates in the media clearly show that the risk from permafrost thaw on the built environment is contested. While some readily ascribe infrastructure failure to permafrost thaw, others dismiss this correlation as "climate myths" (Skjæraasen, Helledal & Klausen 2021), and rather point to bad engineering and maintenance. This points to a deeper problematic in social science permafrost-thaw research and risk assessments (Rudiak-Gould 2013): permafrost thaw is a slow process, and changes such as a deepening of the active layer with a few centimeters is hard to detect with the naked eye. On the other hand, very visible phenomena such as overwater or mud, are often ascribed to climate change even though they are results of the seasonal thawing of the active layer independently of climate change. Furthermore, this disagreement over the societal impacts of permafrost thaw indicates that these perceptions and related climate change discourses are often politicized and shaped by values, worldviews, and specific agendas. Perceptions of permafrost thaw and related risks thus have to be considered not merely in their material but also in their discursive dimension.

5.4. Northern Sakha (Yakutiya), Russia

5.4.1. Summary

Our greater case study area includes Bulunskiy District, one of the northernmost Arctic areas of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutiya), with more focus on two communities. The town of Tiksi, founded in the heydays of Soviet development of the Arctic and still proudly called "the Arctic sea-gate of Yakutiya" and is a maritime and riverine transportation node and the center of the Bulunskiy Ulus (District) of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutiya) in Russia. The neighboring indigenous village Bykovskiy is an indigenous fishing settlement. After the reconfiguration of the transportation system, the major bulk of foods and goods is supplied to Tiksi from Ust'-Kut by the Lena River during the navigation season, and from Yakutsk on winter roads during the

ice season. The current modernization program of the Northern Sea Route (NSR) so far remains an unfulfilled promise and the socio-economic and population decline characterize the district.

The growing environmental changes that both communities are facing include impacts of thawing permafrost on stability and functioning of infrastructures, mobility, subsistence and supply. In Bykovskiy, thawing permafrost has been destroying a sacred site (a cemetery) and affecting subsistence activities (fishing) and ice cellars. Yet, local residents, preoccupied with socio-economic concerns, seem to ignore environmental changes. We argue that this “ignorance” is caused not by lack of local environmental knowledge and expertise, but by a combination of pervasive modernization ideologies, preoccupation with the immediate issues of economic survival, and lack of power and financial resources for mitigation of large-scale effects of environmental change on the local level.

5.4.2. Case study site description

Tiksi was founded in 1932 as a port city of the NSR during the heyday of Soviet exploration, urbanization and industrialization of the Arctic. Located at the delta of the Lena River, it became a vibrant urban settlement, an important transshipment node and later also a headquarter to a military base. In the year of 1989, which marked the community’s population and development peak, its local population exceeded 11,000 and the sea port was bustling with cargo ships delivering an assortment of goods and foods to local residents (Gukov, 2013; Struchkov, 2005). In the post-Soviet years, Tiksi as most of other communities in the Russian Arctic, has been experiencing population decline, reconfiguration of transportation system and socio-economic transformations. The current national program of modernization of the NSR filled with the promises of community development, has been remaining only on paper. The present permanent (civilian) population counts up to ca 4600 residents, with roughly one third of Sakha (Yakut) people, one third of indigenous numerically small groups (primarily, Evenki and Eveny people), and one third of Russian settlers. Most of them are employed in local fishing economy, small-scale trade, and public services.

The rural community of Bykovskiy is located on the Bykovskiy Peninsula, 40 km away by sea from Tiksi. It is the largest indigenous (primarily Evenki) fishing community in the Bulunskiy District founded in 1940 during the Soviet collectivization and sedentization of nomadic population. Forced relocations and deportation of political prisoners from the Baltic states to the area in the 1940-1950s added to the ethnic diversity but also to the dark past of the community. Post-Soviet socio-economic transformations resulted in the reorganization of fishing economy and competition for marine resources with non-local stakeholders. However, the local fishing enterprise “Kolkhoz “Arktika”” still keeps most of the population occupied, while also providing basic social security and access to subsistence resources (fish and others) to slightly over 500 local residents (Gorokhov, 2002; Stammer et al. 2017)

5.4.3. Objective

Both communities have been observing and experiencing a number of growing environmental changes, including shifting of seasons, extreme weather events, and transformations of

cryosphere and landscapes, that are in many cases connected with permafrost thaw (Lantuit et al. 2011). The most visible change caused by permafrost thaw is severe progressing coastal erosion in Bykovskiy affecting houses and destroying the sacred site (the grave-yard). Other significant changes resulting from permafrost thaw and reported to us include malfunctioning of ice roads, transformation of the land cover and vegetation of the tundra, and appearance of the mammoth tusk from the melting ground.

While Soviet modernization ideologies (Slavin, 1982) justified human-induced environmental changes as inevitable costs of progress, engineering and natural scientists offered state-supported adaptation solutions for construction of buildings and transport infrastructures on permafrost. During the post-Soviet socio-economic crisis, local coastal communities have to adapt to multiple changes and challenges, and those having immediate and straightforward effects on local livelihoods were given priority. But even in most dramatic cases (like the destruction of the grave-yard or seasonal disruption of community supply), financial resources allocated by the state are scarce and local consequences are mitigated (or not) by top-down decisions. This case study sought to identify environmental risks (especially those posed by permafrost thaw) in the process of adaptation of Arctic coastal communities to multiple infrastructural, socio-economic and environmental changes in the Soviet and post-Soviet periods. In our research, we tried to address the question: Why do local residents seem to ignore or downplay even the most obvious environmental changes that they have been leaving with? While looking for the answer to this question, we paid special attention to the entanglements between the natural, the built and social environments as constituents of the overall quality of life, sustainability and well-being of local communities.

5.4.4. Methods

The data used in this case study were collected during the anthropological fieldwork in the capital city of Yakutsk and the communities of Tiksi and Bykovskiy in the Republic of Sakha (Yakutiya) in July 2019. Our fieldwork methods included observations, community meetings, focus groups and in-depth interviews with local and indigenous residents, expert interviews with representatives of administrations and NGOs, as well as work with local archives. Our fieldwork started with a series of meetings in research institutes and public organizations in Yakutsk and continued with an introductory community meeting accompanied by a round table discussion in the local administration in Tiksi. In the process of the main fieldwork, 3 focus groups and 22 interviews with the residents and experts, as well as the current local reports on and plans of socio-economic development were gathered. While we initially intended to return to the region in order to conduct follow-up fieldwork and a community workshop on local risks and adaptations to permafrost thaw, the COVID-19 pandemic and later Russia's war in Ukraine made these plans for further research impossible and recently reduced the earlier established contacts with local research partners and institutions.

5.4.5. Results

The analysis of our field data has shown that despite of being preoccupied with socio-economic issues, residents of the studied communities of northern Sakha (Yakutiya) do have a number of environmental concerns directly or indirectly connected to thawing permafrost. Local and regional experts' opinions prove and contextualize these concerns in a broader social, economic and political context. Like in many other coastal Arctic communities on permafrost, people in Bykovskiy and Tiksi are worried about stability of infrastructure built on degrading permafrost or eroding ground (especially, along the coast in Bykovskiy). There is a number of concerns about health and well-being due to overall environmental degradation and pollution of water, air and ground that are linked to more specific concerns about food security, subsistence activities and being in nature. Thawing permafrost also entails a number of economic losses and investments needed to mitigate its consequences. Average residents, especially indigenous herders and fishermen are concerned with carrying the costs of melting ice cellars, growing shrubbification and swampiness of the tundra pastures. Travelling on the tundra has become more dangerous because of the unexpected transformations of the landscape; likewise, going out into the sea has become riskier because of less predictable and extreme weather and ice conditions. Experts are concerned about the lack of funds and decision-making power needed for local mitigation measures (coastal protection, rebuilding and moving of houses) against devastating impacts of coastal erosion. One specific growing activity – extraction of mammoth tusk appearing from the thawing permafrost, became an economic opportunity for some non-indigenous residents and newcomers. However, it is a problem for most of the population due the landscape transformation and damage that it causes to archeological sites and subsistence activities. Finally, the perceptions of environmental changes, including impacts and risks of the permafrost thaw are culturally marked and depend on the perspectives and experiences of interlocutors.

5.4.1. Summary of perceived key risks

	Key risks (perceived)	Interview quotes (Examples)
Infrastructure and built environment	<p>Destruction of buildings and sacred sites (e.g., due to coastal erosion in Bykovskiy)</p> <p>Malfunctioning of ice roads</p> <p>Damages to paved roads and airstrips</p> <p>Decreased reliability of ice cellars</p>	<p>“Yes, it seems that the cape has been melting away. It [the coastal erosion] progresses every year...In 2012, it degraded a lot and half the cemetery was washed away at once. Now it has somehow slowed down. And now we just do not build anything in this direction of the village any more. We do not put up houses there. And we demolish and move all the older buildings standing there to this part of the village. This is the only way ...”</p>
Health and wellbeing	<p>Concern about pollution of water and marine resources</p> <p>Concern with technological hazards, e.g., industrial pollution, chemical and oil spills</p>	<p>“During ebb-and-float, water flowing downstream is dirty, I guess, because they open those dams...Of course, the water looks awful and one can catch yellow fishes then”</p>

	<p>Concern about soil contamination due to outbreak of (dormant) viral diseases (e.g., anthrax) because of the destruction of cemeteries</p> <p>Decrease quality of indoor environment, e.g., mold and disrepair in houses</p> <p>Higher dependence on low quality foods supplied to local stores leading to health problems</p> <p>Concern about possible exposure to environmental contaminants, causing neurobehavioral, reproductive, cardiovascular, endocrine and carcinogenic effects</p>	
<p>Economy and material wellbeing</p>	<p>Economic challenges and financial loss, e.g. due disruptions and higher costs of supply of foods and fuels because of malfunctioning ice roads (high snow and shortening period of use)</p> <p>Economical losses due to repair, decommission and moving of buildings affected by subsidence and erosion</p> <p>Losses to subsistence economy due to shrinking fishing stocks and loss of reindeer pastures because of landscape transformations (swamps, shrubification)</p> <p>Loss of food and economic profit because of melting ice cellars use for keeping fish for own consumption and market sales (especially in Bykovskiy)</p> <p>Lacking funds for local coastal protection measures</p> <p>Extraction of mammoth tusk (appearing because of PFT thaw) with water jets destroys tundra landscapes and creates losses to subsistence economy</p>	<p>„Earlier we had extremely cold weather and opened [ice roads] in December. And now we only do it in January. This is connected with global warming. The shortening season [of ice roads] is a challenge. We need to hurry up to deliver coal and lubricants. For example, here in the northeast, the impacts of warming have been sensible“</p> <p>„We tried to take measures for coastal protection, but even the republic [the Republic of Sakha] cannot allocate us so much funds. These should be some kind of federal money“</p> <p>“Activities of so called “black mammoth diggers” in the North have negative impacts. When they use water jets, as far as I know, for excavations on the ground, it might change the waterways of small rivers”</p>

<p>Culture and Language</p>	<p>Concern about loss/maintenance of cultural, tangible and intangible heritage</p> <p>Concern for impacts on culture, identity, language, social fragmentation</p> <p>Culturally defined attitudes to destruction of sacred sites by permafrost thaw (coastal erosion)</p> <p>Illegal extraction and collection of mammoth tusk (appearing because of permafrost thaw) destroys archeological and cultural heritage sites</p>	<p>That nearby island is called “cemeterial” (<i>mogil’nyi</i>) although there no single grave there. In childhood, I was always wondering what kind of cemetery could be there in the middle of fisheries. And then I learned that those people (deported prisoners) were buried there, but all these have already been washed away...And here they (graves) will be standing as long as the cape exists. Where should one place it? Who will rebury them?</p>
<p>Water and food security</p>	<p>Concern about food security (e.g. fish) stored in ice cellars</p> <p>Concern about shrinking fish stocks</p> <p>Concern about adverse effects on aquatic ecosystems, such as loss of biodiversity</p> <p>Concern about changing nutrient fluxes and respective impacts on fresh water supply</p>	<p>„Ice cellars are melting. Last year one cellar was flooded. There were big rains and high precipitation. They thawed the ground and soaked the ground. Ice cellar itself can keep the normal negative temperature suitable for food storage only till the midsummer. Then it cools down only to minus 3 or minus five. Then it’s already hard to preserve fish“</p> <p>„The fish stock has been diminishing. It all depends on climate. The nearby waters have been desalinating. And the food for the fish habitating in sea water – small fishes and bugs – has been disappearing. Because of the lack of food, fish migrates away from the shore deeper into the sea“</p>
<p>Fate control, including planning</p>	<p>Planning of new infrastructures and resource development on territories with continuous permafrost need to take into consideration expert recommendations</p> <p>Local communities are challenged with the lack of financial resources and decision-making power to mitigate impacts of permafrost thaw</p> <p>Uncertainty arises regarding future investment, potential loss of home, or need for relocation</p>	<p>“Road construction organizations do not want to take mitigation measures that we recommend – they just monitor ...”</p> <p>“There is a center for strategic planning. They call us and ask where and what can be developed. And we write them detailed recommendations about each region and location: e.g., here one cannot develop land because of the ice ... But they never inform us about their plans.”</p>

	<p>Challenges regarding recruitment, retainment, and education of qualified staff in remote communities</p> <p>Continuous out-migration (esp. of youth) caused by hard living conditions in the North</p> <p>Need for new food and water sources may arise</p>	
Recreation and Being in nature	A wetter tundra is harder to walk across, and river bank and hillside erosion leads to changes in navigable paths, river channels,	
Travel and transportation (Mobility & Supply)	<p>Access to fisheries is more complicated because of fish migrations caused by changing quality of water</p> <p>Traveling on the tundra has become dangerous because of the transformation of landscapes (more swamps)</p> <p>Loss of connectivity between and within settlements and camps, e.g., roads may get closed, rivers become unnavigable due to the effects of permafrost thaw</p>	<p>“It is dangerous to fish far away out of the open sea. There are ice cracks and built-ups. There are strong winds and big waves. When the winds are that strong, they don’t go fishing”</p> <p>“When you travel with a <i>Buran</i> (a snowmobile) across the tundra, you can notice that a shore from the last year had disappeared. You can only bewilder if it was washed away, melted away, or something else happened to it. Such transformations have been going on and on. There are always swampy areas here. For example, in autumn it is particularly dangerous to travel on the tundra. Once we had a case when a snowmobile got lost and was never found”</p>

5.4.2. Conclusion

As documented in the table above, the people residing in Tiksi and Bykovskiy are well aware of the many dimensions of environmental change occurring in and around their communities. At the same time, socio-economic issues seem to be more prevalent among the residents’ concerns. As elsewhere in the Russian Arctic, post-Soviet transformations have severely impacted the two communities in question, resulting in different degrees of social, cultural and economic problems and hardships. While Tiksi has experienced severe economic and demographic decline, Bykovskiy seems to have weathered these transformations relatively

well. The differences have to do with the specific historic trajectories and economic orientations of the communities in question. While the past and present of Tiksi has been tied to the Northern Sea Route and military posts, Bykovskiy has been and continues to be a fishing village.

Indigenous and non-indigenous residents of the region have a long history of observing extreme weather events, shifts in seasonal patterns, and changes in the behavior of land animals and fish (Graybill 2013; Ksenofontov et al. 2017). At the same time, Soviet and post-Soviet knowledge hierarchies do not put a lot of emphasis on this kind of local knowledge but privilege outside “expert” knowledge instead. In addition, the above-mentioned pervasive Soviet (and, to a lesser degree, post-Soviet) modernization ideologies have impacted how much attention has been given to narratives about changing environments by people living “traditional” lifestyles, that is subsistence users. In short, our interlocutors did not “ignore” environmental change but considered other transformations in the region more important during our conversations with them. There are several reasons for that but missing environmental knowledge is not among them.

5.5. Results from a survey in three Arctic communities on the impact of permafrost thaw on subsistence activities.

A major integration component of the Nunataryuk social science work packages was a survey on perceived impacts of permafrost thaw, in the form of collectively designed questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of 42 open and closed questions divided into three sections: 1) perceived social impacts and adaptation to permafrost degradation; 2) subsistence activities and permafrost degradation; 3) ethnicity, gender, age, and health profile of the participants. The questionnaire was distributed in three study sites: Aklavik, Canada; Qeqertarsuaq, Greenland; and Longyearbyen, Svalbard (Norway). It was translated and adapted to the local context and languages. For Aklavik and Qeqertarsuaq, local field assistants were hired to conduct the survey. Survey answers were collected between February 2019 and October 2020. In total, 237 people took part in the survey (Aklavik: 53; Longyearbyen: 84; Qeqertarsuaq: 100).

IMPACT OF PERMAFROST THAW ON SUBSISTENCE ACTIVITIES

We have reported on the results of the survey in several publications and Nunataryuk deliverables (Jungsberg et al. 2021, Ramage et al. 2020, Ramage et al. 2022, Vanderlinden et al. 2020). The survey results provide a good indication of locally perceived risks related to permafrost, which in this report are complemented by qualitative data. The profiles of the three permafrost coastal communities are contrasting and the questionnaire shows that the perceived impacts of permafrost thaw varies considerably between the communities, as outlined in detail in the publications listed above. Less people engaged in subsistence activities in Longyearbyen while almost all of the respondents in Aklavik and Qeqertarsuaq engaged in hunting, fishing, and harvesting.

Physical changes observed in all sites are changes in the sea ice thickness and season as well as erosion and slumping. Permafrost thaw had an impact on the subsistence activities in Aklavik but not so much in Qeqertarsuaq or Longyearbyen. (Ramage et al. 2022; Timlin et al 2021, 2022a, 2022b). In Qeqertarsuaq, permafrost thaw is perceived as a challenge mainly in the realms of hunting and harvesting, culture, and infrastructure. Hunting and harvesting activities, as well as culture and infrastructure, are the areas which are perceived as most impacted by permafrost thaw in Aklavik, whereas in Longyearbyen the societal challenge most people associate with permafrost thaw, is its impacts on housing, buildings and infrastructure.

6. Concluding remarks

The risk framework has provided an effective foundation for conducting research in co-production with local residents and stakeholders on the impacts and risks of permafrost thaw.

Overarching themes in all study sites include a focus on the built environment, including heritage sites, since infrastructure is a critical link mediating between physical processes and social impacts. Further, subsistence, linked to health, food security and cultural vitality is of paramount importance in all study sites except Longyearbyen, which does not have an Indigenous population, although also on Svalbard subsistence hunting and fishing play a role in food security.

Interview results show that perceived key risks from permafrost thaw in Ilulissat are associated with all life domains but particularly with infrastructure and built environment, economy and material wellbeing, and fate control and planning, whereas risks to other life domains - health and wellbeing, water and food security, and cultural wellbeing - are less likely to be attributed specifically or solely to permafrost thaw. In the case of Beaufort Sea Region, Yukon Coast and Mackenzie River Delta, Canada, increased permafrost thaw is largely considered having a negative impact on life, with infrastructure failure being a main concern. In Longyearbyen, Svalbard, people generally associate permafrost thaw with negative changes. Many participants emphasized that permafrost thaw does not cause problems to them personally, a finding that was confirmed in the survey conducted. Permafrost thaw is by most participants perceived as a societal rather than a personal risk. Also, permafrost thaw is not the change that seems most pressing to most people in Longyearbyen in a time of drastic societal and climatic changes. In the case of Northern Sakha (Yakutiya), Russia, field data has shown that despite being preoccupied with socio-economic issues, residents of the studied communities of northern Sakha (Tiksi and Bykovskiy) do have a number of environmental concerns directly or indirectly connected to thawing permafrost.

In general, the data collected suggest that what local residents emphasize and how they rate the risks from permafrost thaw depends on their role, responsibility, and general life situation. Finally, it is important to note that permafrost thaw is a phenomenon difficult to understand for most non-experts, especially as the perceivable changes are happening very slowly. Overall, the conceptual risk framework with its compass model and methodological flow chart where we incorporate the dual dimensions of risk has been shown to be an effective framework for studying thawing permafrost in Arctic coastal communities. The model provides a useful approach to the identification and gathering of coastal risks, to make assessments and to apply different tools and analysis for empowering local communities to effectively manage and respond to risks from thawing permafrost. The combination of the conceptual and processual model can be used for guiding large multidisciplinary projects, such as Nunataryuk, in identifying major risks from climate change in co-production with local communities and stakeholders.

The next step is to conduct three risk workshops co-funded by the University of the Arctic; the first one to be held in Ilulissat, Greenland; the second in Inuvik, Canada; and the third and final one in Longyearbyen, Svalbard. The purpose of these workshops is to discuss, share, and validate the research results on key risks from permafrost thaw with local communities. This will serve as a platform for feedback and discussion with Indigenous and local people, policymakers and other stakeholders, including other scientists. This will contribute important input for the next steps on designing Arctic social and bio-physical indicators, and adaptation and mitigation strategies in co-production with local residents and stakeholders in each of our case study regions. The work on developing Arctic social and biophysical indicators and adaptation and mitigation strategies contributes to reducing the identified key risks from permafrost thaw.

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